

Covid-19 induced accelerated development of digital platforms within the agricultural sector

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the influence of the Covid -19 pandemic on the digitalization acceleration regarding the agriculture sector. This influence is first viewed from an IT governance perspective and is then clarified by means of a case study on BPI and Cybersecurity applications.

Keywords

Agriculture, digital platforms, centralized platforms, Covid-19

1 INTRODUCTION

As everybody is noticing, we are currently living in a strange period of time, namely a pandemic. This pandemic has disrupted the way of living and working of most people. In this paper it will be examined what the influence of covid-19 is on the digitization of the agriculture sector. This sector is mentioned a lot in combination with the pandemic because of the many negative effects associated with it. For example since the covid-19 outbreak a lot of bars and restaurants all over the world had to close their doors, this affects the agriculture business since the bars and restaurants are buying less food. That covid-19 has an impact on the sector is clear, but what will this pandemic have for impact on the digitization of the agriculture sector. Traditionally this is a conservative sector, where digitizing is not embraced in every part of the industry. Will this be the time where agriculture has to change? Yes, a report from India (pahuja, 2020), where Bayer, a seeds and traits company, is one of the biggest companies in the industry, mentioned that the farmers in India normally got face to face training to introduce new methods and industry specific applications. In this study we will examine this from three different viewpoints. The first one is the IT governance viewpoint, here will be examined what the impact of using digital platforms is on the industry. The second one is the business process

integration viewpoint, here the process of face to face advice to digital advice will be compared and thirdly from a cyber security perspective.

2 RESEARCH

2.1 OBJECTIVE

The impact that the covid-19 virus has on society can be described as ubiquitous. To narrow down the scope of this research, this paper will mainly focus on the effects that the pandemic has on the agriculture sector.

Looking from a global perspective, this traditional sector has been reluctant to adopt new technologies, even though these new technologies may boost their production size or could help finding new clients by changing the way they can distribute their production. A country such as The Netherlands may lead the way in the adoption of new technologies in the agricultural sector, but many (third world) countries are still lagging. This is partly because they do not have the financial resources that are needed to invest in these (physical) technologies.

Now, as a result of the outbreak of the pandemic, the development of new platforms that can support farmers around the world may have accelerated. Therefore, this research will focus on the effects of the pandemic on the agricultural sector and the extent to which this pandemic has led to the accelerated development and use of digitized platforms.

2.2 APPROACH

In this part of the paper, we will describe how the research is structured and the approach that has been chosen. Here we will describe how we will fulfill the research objective to analyse the impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the digital transformation in the agriculture sector. According to Simon Wiebusch, the Chief Operating Officer (COO) of the Crop Science Division of Bayer for India, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka, there are currently projects on chatbots, predictive advice, e-commerce intervention, and

video conferencing. They are not in one platform integrated yet, but Bayer Crop Science sees it as the ultimate goal to create a platform that can be used as one-point interaction for the farmer (Pahuja, 2020).

Based on this information, and the limitation of time, the decision has been made to focus on the use of platforms in the agriculture sector to analyse the impact of digital transformation in the field of IT governance. In order to learn more about the impact on specific business processes, there is chosen to focus on the digital transformation regarding platforms for Bayer Crop Science. For the field of business process integration, there is decided to focus on the digital transformation of the advice process, which will be transformed from face to face meetings to a virtual meeting place, and be included in the desired platform.

For this research, literature will be used. This data will be collected through news articles and information from the Bayer Crop Science website, to learn more about the current digital transformation in the agriculture sector. Based on this information, academic papers will be analysed and the methods and theories from these papers will be applied and compared with the current developments.

3 AGRICULTURE AND FOOD

The worldwide agriculture sector includes a large number of companies ranging from small to large. These companies are in the practice and science of producing crops and livestock from natural resources. Our planet has in total around 570 million farms (S. Lowder, 2015). Nowadays the agriculture sector is both fully commercial and using modern technologies. All these companies together form a chain in which primary agricultural production and industrial processing takes place. Recent developments aim to reduce negative impacts on our climate and increase sustainability. The sector wants to achieve this in the following ways: Knowledge & innovation, Sustainability, International agreements, Start-ups. Because agriculture is practised worldwide, the largest companies are located in the largest economies. The number one in terms of yearly revenue (114.7 billion) is an American agricultural and food production giant named Cargill. This company provides for almost one quarter of the American meat and grain exports and is involved in almost every step of the agriculture supply chain. Next to that they are an industry leader in animal nutrition science and active in about 40 countries with almost 166 000 employees. Deere & Company is standing in number five with almost 40 billion in revenue. The firm is number one in producing vast arrays of agriculture equipment including tractors, combines, harvesters and cotton pickers. They also make smaller equipment such as

lawn mowers, cutters and shredders and tractors. The sector agriculture & food has an important relationship with the transportation sector. Agricultural crops produced must undergo a series of operations while in the supply chain such as harvesting, threshing, winnowing, bagging, transportation, storage, processing and trade before they enter the market and there are significant losses in crop production at all these stages, as is evident from several studies across the world (I. Somashekhar, 2014). In this type of supply chain there are four main actors namely: retailers, distributors, processors and farmers. These four actors are in a so called network which is called very complex in which each firm is positioned in a network layer and at least belongs to one supply chain and most of the time has multiple suppliers or customers.

There are several factors that drive diversity between the agriculture sector and other sectors. SCM of perishable food produce is complex as compared to other SCMs due to the perishable nature of the produce, high fluctuations in demand and prices, increasing consumer concerns for food safety & quality (Vorst & Beulens, 2002), and dependence on climate conditions (Salin, 1998). Agriculture has multiple subcategories ranging from aquaculture (not using soil) to viticulture (growing grapes). In total there are 25 sub-categories counting livestock. This means that the sector is very diverse and that the needed knowledge in order to be successful or different types of transformations can greatly differ per category (Bayer, 2020).

Key developments

The key developments that the sector has undergone in recent years are mostly related to IoT and industry 4.0. Connectivity is the core in these developments and IoT is the most important enabling technology that is indispensable within agricultural equipment these days.

Digitalisation of the agriculture sector is based on technologies such as AI, automations, data analytics and predictive analytics. Examples of this are automations. Automations can increase productivity by reducing the need of human effort. In practice this is seen in several forms such as automated vehicles, robots or automated parts of production processes.

For predictive analytics there is now the ability to collect more valuable data such as soil quality, irrigation levels, weather data and presence of certain insects and pests. With this data predictions can be made and automations triggered.

To take advantage of these key developments, the agriculture sector sees the development of IoT platforms. The strategy of players (often major players in the industry like equipment manufacturers

such as John Deere or crop suppliers such as Cargill as mentioned above) is to develop themselves through both technical and data channels in a dominant position. In setting standards and securing the market early on, the position of technology platforms, based on the control of technological enables, can be significant (Vincent bonneau, Bertrand Copigneaux, Laurent Probst, Bertrand Pedersen 2017).

4 ANALYSIS
4.1 IT GOVERNANCE AND STRATEGIC SOURCING

To analyze the impact of the digital transformation on the IT governance of an agriculture firm, we will start to describe the current situation. Afterwards the desired situation for IT governance will be discussed. The section will conclude with a description of the changes that are needed. To analyze the IT governance of the firm there is decided to use the Governance Design Matrix from Weill (2004). This matrix will give insights in the style in which the input is provided and how the decisions are made. The Governance Design Matrix has two variables, the style and the domain. The styles are also known as IT Governance Archetypes. The following IT Governance Archetypes are taken into account:

- Business monarchy (individual or group of business executives)
- IT monarchy (individual or group of IT executives)
- Feudal (business unit leaders)
- Federal (c-level executives and business groups)
- IT Duopoly (IT executives and one other group)
- Anarchy (each individual user) (Weill & Ross, 2004).

The domains that are used in the matrix are:

- IT principles (high level statements about how IT is used in the business)
- IT architecture (set of technical choices to guide the organization in satisfying business needs)
- IT infrastructure (strategies for the base foundation of IT capability, shared throughout the firm as reliable services, and centrally coordinated)
- Business application needs (specifying the business need for purchased or internally developed IT applications)
- IT investment and prioritization (decisions about how much and where to invest in IT) (Weill & Ross, 2004).

The archetypes and domains discussed above are used to fill in the IT Governance Design Matrix for

the agriculture sector in the current situation. For the desired situation, we looked at the characteristics of platform related IT Governance, as this is the desired situation.

The current situation

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Archetype	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy										
IT Monarchy		X		X		X		X		X
Feudal										
Federal										
IT Duopoly	X		X		X		X		X	
Anarchy										

Table I: IT governance of the current situation

For creating the current situation, secondary information is used. A research conducted by R. Huang, R.W. Zmud, and R.L. Price to the IT Governance of an agriculture firm with 300 employees, and the compliance policy of Bayer. In order to create the IT Governance Design Matrix, both policies are taken into account. The research conducted by R. Huang et al. showed that the company had a centralized approach in the form of a CIO. No formal steering committees were used, and there was informal involvement from senior divisional executives. The CIO had mentioned the following in an interview:

“Now as those things (building an infrastructure) have been put in place, and hopefully become reliable and functional, we’ve tried to turn towards what tools we need from a business perspective, and from an operational perspective. Those decisions in terms of what we need are ultimately mine.” (Huang, Zmud, Price, 2009).

Based on this information the input section of the model was completed in table I with almost all input from the IT executives and the informal involvement of divisional executives. As this is an agriculture firm employing 300 employees, the governance of the large multinational Bayer is also analyzed. They mention that the most important tasks of the Board of Management are defining corporate strategy, setting the budget and allocating corporate resources (Bayer, 2020).

The desired new situation

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Archetype	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy										X
IT Monarchy				X		X				
Feudal										
Federal	X		X		X		X		X	
IT Duopoly		X						X		
Anarchy										

Table II: IT governance of the desired situation

The new situation in table II that is examined in this research has already been started ahead of the Covid-19 situation, but the Covid-19 has accelerated this digital transformation. In the case of Bayer this transformation is in the form of the development of a platform. This platform is a combination of an exchange and service platform. The exchange part of the platform provides an online marketplace where buyers and sellers negotiate and trade. The service part of the platform provides an online place where buyers or farmers can ask questions or get consults, where this previously took place in real life. This change from a traditional agriculture organization to a digital platform introduces the necessary changes in the area of IT governance (Jagt, 2020; Assaubayeva & Wong Bi YI, 2020; CGTN, 2020).

To make the platform perform successfully, it is important that IT and the business are properly aligned. The business has to provide input to fulfill their IT demands. They have to represent the needs of the customer. The IT principles will be decided by the IT executives and C-level executives. The CIO will decide on the IT Architecture and the IT infrastructure, based on input from C-level (IT) executives and business groups. These federal arrangements are used to incorporate business strategies considerations. As the operations become more specific it is important to collect input from the business groups as they represent the customers needs and understand the requirements from the business and the customers. They can also give an indication of the investment that is needed for their business. The IT executives and C-level executives will eventually decide on the application needs, and the C-level executives will decide on the investment that needs to be made.

4.2 BUSINESS PROCESS INTEGRATION

As mentioned earlier, bayer is working to implement a two sided platform combining the exchange of goods on one side and the consulting services on the other side. In order to illustrate how Bayer is working on this in practice, we created two BPMN processes based on the digital transformation

process for farmers working with the company Bayer. This new process is based on the service side of the platform and consists of digital consulting for farmers. The first process is based on the current situation and the second proces on the previous situation.

The process (see appendix figure II) starts with the farmer, the farmer has a need for information and in the new situation can use an online platform on his/her smartphone to sign in to Bayer’s network. When the communication/login is successful it can create a request for new knowledge. If the request has been made the system will check if the needed knowledge is in the knowledge database. If so the correct knowledge will automatically be given to the farmer. If not, the farmer gets into a call with an agent from Bayer. The Agent will give the needed knowledge and the farmer can interpret it. When the advice call ends there will be no contact for 7 days and then the evaluation form is sent, when the farmer is not satisfied an agent from Bayer will make a call to stress out potential issues.

The older process (see appendix figure I) starts with a request for information, to gather this knowledge the farmer can travel to the desired location from Bayer, where he retrieves knowledge and expresses it’s need for knowledge. The advice will be interpreted and when fully satisfied the process will end. One of the major advantages of the new digital consulting process compared to the previous version is the difference in traveling time. There is no need for farmers to attend physically when they are provided with advice.

4.3 CYBER SECURITY

As stated above the agricultural discipline was already on pace with digital transformation even before COVID. COVID now speeds up the process of digital transformation even more. This change also increases the likelihood of cybersecurity risks because the unpredictable times sometimes allow for quicker decisions to be made without cybersecurity risk management. In the appendix table III and table IV we have created a list with different cybersecurity risks for agriculture with their impact and likelihood.

		Impact					
		1	2	3	4	5	
likelihood		Trivial	Minor	Moderate	Major	Extreme	
	1	Rare					Risk 3,4,5
	2	Unlikely			Risk 2		
	3	Moderate					Risk 1
	4	Likely		Risk 6,7			
	5	Very likely					

Table III: risk analysis matrix

Risks:

1. Ransomware
2. Data theft/leak
3. Network downtime (jamming)
4. Business email containing frauds
5. Phone scams (phishing)
6. Phishing emails

Type	Likelihood	Impact	Risk
Ransomware	3	5	15
Data theft	2	3	6
Network downtime (jamming)	1	5	5
Losing control of automated systems	1	5	5
Losing control of autonomous vehicles	1	5	5
Business email containing frauds	4	2	8
Phone scams (phishing)	4	2	8

Table IV: risk analysis calculation

For all risks we have created a combined list with mitigations for the cyber security risks. (20 CHG controls) (SANS Institute, 2009)

1. Inventory of Authorized and Unauthorized Hardware.
2. Inventory of Authorized and Unauthorized Software.
3. Secure Configurations for Hardware and Software For Which Such Configurations Are Available.
4. Secure Configurations of Network Devices Such as Firewalls And Routers.
5. Boundary Defense
6. Maintenance and Analysis of Complete Security Audit Logs
7. Application Software Security
8. Controlled Use of Administrative Privileges
9. Controlled Access Based On Need to Know
10. Continuous Vulnerability Testing and Remediation
11. Dormant Account Monitoring and Control
12. Anti-Malware Defenses
13. Limitation and Control of Ports, Protocols and Services
14. Wireless Device Control
15. Data Leakage Protection
16. Additional Critical Controls (not directly supported by automated measurement and validation): Secure Network Engineering
17. Red Team Exercises
18. Incident Response Capability
19. Assured Data Back-Up
20. Security Skills Assessment and Training to Fill Gaps

5 DISCUSSION

Based on our analysis, we saw that the pandemic has digitally transformed the interaction between suppliers and buyers within the agriculture sector. Due to the measures set by governments for personnel to work as much from home as possible and to socially distance from each other, the suppliers and buyers needed a new way to interact with each other that now also can be utilized by farmers worldwide.

In the case of our research, the suppliers and buyers are the farmers that want to make use of Bayer's consulting services. Based on the analysis, we saw that consulting services are moving to an online form, where farmers can make an appointment for an online meeting with one of Bayer's consultants. This transformation eliminated the need to provide consulting services physically at location and thus required a change in the way the business processes were run. Due to the transformation, the farmers can now access an online knowledge base to find answers to their questions. When their questions could not be solved by this knowledge base, an online call could be arranged with a Bayer consultant and a digital consulting service could be delivered quickly.

Setting up a useful platform required a change in the governance mechanisms. In order to create a useful platform for the farmers (and business consultants), acquiring the input of the business consultants regarding the technical requirements was more important than before. This way, Bayer made sure that the platform met the requirements and was going to be used by the farmers and consultants properly.

Regarding the security aspect of the digital transformation, we discovered that the main vulnerabilities are the ones that are common to IT platforms/applications. This means that especially ransomware attacks can have devastating consequences for the business continuity and therefore need to be mitigated accordingly. In addition to this, due to the GDPR, any theft (or leaks) of personal identifiable information can lead to big financial penalties.

As a result of the pandemic, Bayer accelerated the development of the digitized platform and digitized processes that were analog before. Now, farmers can gather valuable information online and make online appointments with Bayer's consultants. This does not have to be limited to local farmers, instead, farmers around the world that encounter problems with their production can access these services, if they have internet access. These platforms can now play an important part in the globalization of the agriculture sector.

The digital transformation has helped farmers

around the world, because they are now able to independently find solutions to their problems online or, otherwise, get in contact with a consultant quickly. This has effectively improved their time management, because this eliminated their need to travel in order to get advice. In addition to this, the removal of the need to travel also reduced their travel expenses, carbon footprint and other barriers that may exist for farmers in poorer countries (such as the unavailability of local consultants). The combination of these benefits may make this digital transformation a sustainable one.

CONCLUSION

Based on this research, we can conclude that we see a shift happening in the adoption of services by farmers worldwide provided by the built of centralized platforms, which in turn stimulates the globalization of the agriculture sector. This digital transformation required a change in the way the IT governance is handled due to the integration of business needs in order to build a solid platform.

This centralized digital platform does come with new cyber security risks. These risks need to be re-evaluated in the future and based on the re-evaluation, a new mitigation strategy should be created in order to keep the risks of potential breaches as low as possible.

And lastly, the digital consulting service that is delivered in this platform went through a digitalization process and is now fully accessible by using the internet and is available to farmers worldwide.

Based on our research, we discovered that the agriculture sector has gone through a digital transformation in which different offline processes are now digitized and integrated in centralized platforms that are easily accessible by farmers.

Overall, we can conclude that the global pandemic has accelerated the development of these new centralized platforms that can be accessed by farmers in order to guide them with their productions. However, as these platforms have just recently been put to use, it remains unclear whether these platforms will actually be fully adopted by farmers worldwide. To elaborate on this, farmers in third world countries may not even know that these platforms exist, and even if they do, they still need to have access to the internet in order to fully use these platforms. This limitation has not been researched, but is an interesting topic for future researchers.

APPENDIX

TABLE I

The current situation

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Archetype	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy										
IT Monarchy		X		X		X		X		X
Feudal										
Federal										
IT Duopoly	X		X		X		X		X	
Anarchy										

Table 1: IT governance of the current situation

TABLE II

The desired new situation

IT Activities (Input/Decision) Archetype	IT Principles		IT Architecture		IT Infrastructure Strategies		Business Application Needs		IT Investment	
	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision	Input	Decision
Business Monarchy										X
IT Monarchy				X		X				
Feudal										
Federal	X		X		X		X		X	
IT Duopoly		X						X		
Anarchy										

Table 2: IT governance of the desired situation

FIGURE I

FIGURE II

TABLE III

		Impact					
			1	2	3	4	5
likelihood			Trivial	Minor	Moderate	Major	Extreme
	1	Rare					Risk 3,4,5
	2	Unlikely			Risk 2		
	3	Moderate					Risk 1
	4	Likely		Risk 6,7			
	5	Very likely					

TABLE IV

Type	Likelihood	Impact	Risk
Ransomware	3	5	15
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Phone scams (phishing)	4	2	8

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